

OSMOTIC PRESSURE AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF SHELLAC

BY SADHAN BASU

The nature of solvent-solute interaction has been studied from the measurements of osmotic pressure of dilute shellac solutions

Molecular weights of hard and soft resins have been calculated from the osmotic pressure data. They have been found to be in accord with the values previously obtained by other authors.

In a previous communication (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 148) it has been shown from the measurements of viscosity that the shellac dissolves molecularly in so-called good solvents, but with polar solvents there is always some probability of solvent-solute interaction. In the present communication an attempt has been made to confirm the previous observations from osmotic pressure measurements. Further, the calculation of molecular weight has been made from osmotic pressure data, since it eliminates many of the complications encountered in previous methods. In this section measurements have been done with the constituents of shellac, namely, hard and soft resins, after separating them.*

The rise of osmotic pressure with concentration of high polymer solutions has been a subject of great interest in the present time and extensive work has been done on the solutions of proteins (Adair, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, **A**, 108, 627; Pauli and Fent, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, **67**, 288; Sørensen, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1918, **103**, 15), cellulose derivatives (Duclaux, *J. chim. phys.*, 1931, **28**, 537; Obogi and Broda, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, **69**, 172), rubber (Caspary, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1239) and several synthetic polymers (Kemp and Peter, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1941, **33**, 1926; Flory, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, **9**, 660). An excessive increase of osmotic pressure with concentration has been observed in all the cases. If the osmotic pressure be expressed as a power-series in concentration of solute, we get

$$\pi = Ac_2 + Bc_2^2 + Cc_2^3 + \dots \quad (1)$$

where c_2 = concentration of polymer, π = osmotic pressure in atmosphere and A , B , C , etc. are constants. At extremely low dilution, the higher powers of concentration will become negligible, leaving only the expression containing up to the square terms in equation (1)

$$\pi = Ac_2 + Bc_2^2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

which may be written as

$$\pi/c_2 = A + Bc_2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

That is, the graph of π/c_2 against c_2 is a straight line with a slope equal to B and an intercept on π/c_2 axis equal to A .

The value of A is directly connected with the number of particles that are moving independently, *i.e.*, the state of ideal dispersion and consequently with the molecular

* Shellac is known to be a mixture of two resins: (i) hard resin, which constitutes 70% of lac, is a solid, insoluble in ether, while (ii) soft resin, which constitutes about 30% of lac, is a semi-liquid at ordinary temperature and is soluble in ether.

weight M_2 of the dissolved unit. Thus in a dilute solution, where the dispersion is ideal, it is possible to calculate the molecular weight M_2 from Vant Hoff's relation

$$\lim_{c_2 \rightarrow 0} \frac{\pi}{c_2} = \frac{RT}{M_2} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where R = gas constant and T = absolute temperature.

Interpretation of coefficient B in the expression (3) is somewhat difficult. First attempt towards this direction was made by Ostwald (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, **49**, 60) and afterwards thoroughly investigated by Haller (*ibid.*, 1931, **56**, 257), Adair (*loc. cit.*), Burk (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **87**, 237) and others. They traced the second term back to the swelling phenomenon, i.e., to solvent-solute interaction; or, in other words, the term B may be interpreted as a contribution of the forces between the solvent and the solute.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Measurement of osmotic pressure was made by static elevation method, a Herzog's osmotic cell being used for the purpose (Herzog, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, Bodenstein Fistele and, 1931, p. 239). The most difficult part in this experiment was the preparation of the membranes. Cellophane tubes were cut in the form of circular discs, washed thoroughly first with water and then with benzene-alcohol (1:1) mixture. These discs were then swollen in alcohol-water mixture (60:40) for 12 hours. They were then removed and placed in pure alcohol. In using the membranes with solvents other than ethyl alcohol, the membranes were removed from alcohol, treated successively with a mixture of alcohol and the desired solvent, gradually increasing the proportion of the latter in order to replace alcohol from the pores of the membranes and finally they were kept in the pure solvent.

The osmotic pressure, π , in atmosphere was calculated from the relation :

$$\pi = \frac{(h_{obs} - h_0)\rho}{1033}$$

where ρ = the density of the solute, h_{obs} = the observed equilibrium height in cm. and h_0 = the capillary correction. This correction factor had been determined by dipping the capillary in the solution and observing the rise of the solution in the capillary. This was found to be not more than 3 mm. in any case.

Best result is generally obtained with the membranes prepared by swelling cellophane P.T. 600. But since this was not available, ordinary cellophane paper tubes were used. The permeability of the cellophane tubes were low and it took 8 to 12 hours to attain equilibrium. Further, it was not possible to measure osmotic pressure with a variety of solvents using this membrane. The reproducibility of the results with hard resin was within 5 to 7%, while with soft resin it was 3 to 4%.

The range of accuracy in carefully conducted experiment was within 2% as verified with alcoholic solution of glycine.

Separation of hard and soft resins, the two constituents of lac, was effected by the following method: Powdered, dewaxed, lemon shellac (100 g., 100 mesh) was mixed with twice its amount of powdered, purified sand and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet. The ether solution on evaporation left soft resin which was further extracted with petroleum ether to remove any wax. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol, reprecipitated with ether, redissolved in alcohol, and then it was poured into warm water. The hard resin was taken out from water by drawing it into fibre and then dried.

The solvents used were purified and dried by usual methods. The preparation of the solutions was effected by the methods stated in the previous paper (Basu, *loc. cit.*).

The results of osmotic pressure measurements with hard resin solutions in different solvents are given in Tables I-V and the corresponding $\frac{\pi}{c_2} - c_2$ curves in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

n-Butyl alcohol.

c_2 (g./litre)	π (atm.)	π/c_2 (atm.l/g.)
0.1	0.001438	0.01438
0.3	0.004672	0.01624
0.4	0.007000	0.01750
0.6	0.011760	0.01960
0.8	0.017120	0.02140

TABLE II

Ethyl alcohol.

c_2 (g./litre)	π (atm.)	π/c_2 (atm.l/g.)
0.2	0.003176	0.01588
0.5	0.009750	0.01810
0.8	0.016496	0.02062
1.0	0.021700	0.02170

TABLE III

Water (5%) in acetone.

c_2 (g./litre)	π (atm.)	π/c_2 (atm.l/g.)
0.2	0.003740	0.01870
0.5	0.013010	0.02602
0.7	0.021280	0.03040
1.0	0.037300	0.03730

TABLE IV

Water (10%) in acetone.

c_2 (g./litre)	π (atm.)	π/c_2 (atm.l/g.)
0.1	0.001570	0.01570
0.3	0.006240	0.02080
0.5	0.012260	0.02452
0.8	0.024800	0.03100
1.0	0.035800	0.03580

TABLE V

Water (15%) in acetone

c_2 (g./litre)	π (atm.)	π/c_2 (atm.l/g.)
0.3	0.005790	0.01930
0.5	0.011810	0.02362
0.7	0.018844	0.02692
1.0	0.032800	0.03280

The results of osmotic pressure measurements with soft resin solution in different solvents are given in Tables VI to X and the curves in Fig. 2.

TABLE VI

n-Butyl alcohol.

c_2 (g./litre).	π (atm.).	π/c_2 (atm./g.).
0.1	0.005180	0.05180
0.2	0.010464	0.05232
0.3	0.015960	0.05320
0.5	0.027040	0.05408

TABLE VII

Ethyl alcohol.

c_2 (g./litre).	π (atm.).	π/c_2 (atm./g.).
0.2	0.010496	0.05248
0.3	0.015900	0.05300
0.4	0.021312	0.05328
0.5	0.027200	0.05440

TABLE VIII

Water (5%) in acetone.

c_2 (g./litre).	π (atm.).	π/c_2 (atm./g.).
0.1	0.005240	0.05240
0.2	0.010692	0.05348
0.4	0.022112	0.05528

TABLE IX

Water (10%) in acetone.

c_2 (g./litre).	π (atm.).	π/c_2 (atm./g.).
0.2	0.005220	0.05220
0.3	0.010640	0.05320
0.4	0.016260	0.05420

TABLE X

Water (15%) in acetone.

c_2 (g./litre).	π (atm.).	π/c_2 (atm./g.).
0.2	0.010600	0.05300
0.3	0.016176	0.05392
0.5	0.027800	0.05560

The values of B , i.e., the slope of the curves for different solvents for hard and soft resins are given in Table XI.

TABLE XI

Solvent.	B	
	Hard resin.	Soft resin.
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.0093	0.0052
Ethyl alcohol	0.0074	0.0052
5% Water in acetone	0.0255	0.0108
10% Water in acetone	0.0244	0.0100
15% Water in acetone	0.0216	0.0098

The molecular weights for hard and soft resins as calculated from extrapolated

$\frac{\pi}{c_2} - c_2$ values for different solvents are given in Table XII.

TABLE XII

Solvent	Hard resin		Soft resin	
	$(\pi/c_2)_0$	M_2	$(\pi/c_2)_0$	M_2
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.01348	1857.5	0.05120	481.2
Ethyl alcohol	0.01390	1801.0	0.05112	489.8
5% Water in acetone	0.01390	1801.0	0.05120	481.2
10% Water in acetone	0.01360	1841.1	0.05112	489.8
15% Water in acetone	0.01360	1841.1	0.05112	489.8

DISCUSSION

The departure from ideal behaviour in the $\pi/c_2 - c_2$ curve is generally ascribed to solvation, the dissolved particles carrying with them so much solvent that their effective concentration is reduced. Provided they are individually solvated, extrapolation to infinite dilution will eliminate this error. Even if association of the particles occurs, measurements in sufficiently dilute solution would be expected to permit an extrapolation to the unassociated state at infinite dilution.

The extent of the variation of $\pi/c_2 - c_2$ curve depends both on the nature of solvent and that of solute. An attempt to systematize this behaviour has been made by Schulze (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1937, **A**, 180, 1) who based his deductions on the fact that the osmotic pressure is independent of molecular weight in the region above 10% concentration. It is logical to make the further assumption, as was done by Ostwald (*loc. cit.*), that the contribution to osmotic pressure, which is independent of molecular weight, is also a factor at low concentration, and is not negligible in comparison with the Van't Hoff osmotic pressure term. Ostwald traced this effect back to swelling phenomena and used an osmotic pressure equation given by

$$\pi = Ac + Bc^n \quad \dots (5)$$

and found that n was usually nearly 2. Therefore, the term reduces to the same form as equation (3). Schulze, however, used a relation,

$$\frac{\pi}{c} = \frac{RT}{M} + \pi (K/\pi)^{1/\nu} \quad \dots (6)$$

This equation, however, demands that the deviation from ideality will be larger, the lower the molecular weight, while contrary is the case. Further, it has got a serious drawback that it requires solvation to become infinite at infinite dilution which is far from the case.

The values of B for hard and soft resins (Table XI) in *n*-butyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol are extremely small, though not zero. That is, in these solutions the osmotic pressure of the constituents of shellac is nearly proportional to the concentration. This fact suggests that the interaction of the dissolved particles with each other and also the energetic interaction with the solvent are less marked in these cases, confirming thereby our previous assumption that the shellac molecules are not solvated in these solutions. For acetone-water system, however, the values of B are much higher, most probably due to greater solvent-solute interaction, *i.e.*, solvation, the possibility of which has been noticed by Palit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **17**, 537). The values of B in acetone-water system, however, have been found to fall with increasing concentration of water. Since water is a non-solvent for shellac, it tends to precipitate shellac out of the solution as the concentration is increased, although up to a certain low concentration, water increases the solubility of shellac. As the particles tend to separate and agglomerate at higher concentrations of water, the interacting forces between the solvent and solute, and the solute and solute are gradually altered. Consequently, the values of B become difficult to be computed unless the various thermodynamic constants (*viz.*, heat capacity, chemical constant, ideal mixing, entropy, etc.) of these systems, while surrounded by molecules of its own species and also by molecules of different species, are known.

FIG. 1
Hard resin

method is also open to the objection as at the high temperature employed (176°) a part of resin may undergo polymerisation and the value actually obtained may not represent the true molecular weight of the original sample. In the osmotic pressure method all these difficulties and objections are absent since it uses a very low concentration and ordinary temperature.

From Table XII the molecular weights, calculated for hard and soft resins from osmotic pressure data in different solvents, appear to be fairly consistent though these values for molecular weight may not be obtained for all the samples, since an absolutely pure sample cannot be prepared by the methods available at present. These values may be compared with the values 1900-2000 obtained for hard resin and those of 513-556 obtained for soft resin by Palit and Bhattacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 258). For some samples, values found by these authors in case of hard resin varied from 1400 to 2000.

The author wishes to express his gratefulness to Dr. P.K. Bose, Director, Indian Lac Research Institute, Namkum, for his keen interest and constant encouragement in the present investigation.

In determining the molecular weights of the constituents of shellac in different solvents, namely acetic acid, dioxan, etc., the cryoscopic method has generally been used. But in this method the concentration of shellac should be sufficient to attain appreciable depression of freezing point and thus doubts have been expressed by several workers regarding the propriety of using this method on account of the possibility of association taking place in solution. Rast's

FIG. 2
Soft resin

